

EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF ENGLISH CLASSES FOR NON – PHILOLOGICAL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The importance of English proficiency in today's globalized world is undeniable. As a second language, English is often learned by students from various fields of study, including non-philological disciplines. Non-philological students, such as those studying engineering, medicine, economics, or natural sciences, face unique challenges in learning English compared to their peers in language-focused disciplines. This paper explores effective methods and strategies for organizing English classes specifically tailored for non-philological students. It discusses key pedagogical approaches, identifies common learning obstacles, and proposes solutions to optimize language acquisition. By focusing on task-based learning, content-based instruction, and student-centered activities, this paper outlines a framework that enhances the overall language learning experience for non-philological students.*

Keywords: *effective organization, non-philological, language-learning potential, language skills, vocabulary, technological tools.*

In an era where English is often regarded as the global lingua franca, its importance cannot be overstated. Whether for academic purposes, professional communication, or social integration, proficiency in English has become a vital skill for students across all fields of study. While language and literature majors are immersed in English from the start of their academic careers, non-philological students – those studying subjects like engineering, business, science, and medicine – typically encounter English as a secondary skill. Despite its importance, these students often face distinct challenges in learning the language.

The key challenge lies in the need to balance discipline-specific knowledge with language acquisition. Unlike philological students, who are constantly engaged in language-rich activities, non – philological students tend to view English as a tool for communication rather than a subject of study in itself. Therefore, organizing English classes for non-philological students requires a tailored approach that recognizes their specific needs, interests, and academic goals.

This paper examines the unique challenges faced by non-philological students in learning English and proposes an effective pedagogical framework for designing and organizing English classes that maximize the language-learning potential of these students [Ergashevich 2021: 514].

Before delving into the organization of English classes, it is important to understand the specific challenges that non-philological students encounter in the language-learning process. These challenges include:

1. Lack of Motivation and Relevance – Non-philological students often perceive English as a non-essential skill, something they need to pass exams or for reading academic papers but not a tool for effective communication in their specific field. As such, their motivation for learning the language may be limited, especially when compared to students majoring in languages or humanities, who are more intrinsically motivated to learn English.

2. Limited Exposure to English – While philological students are surrounded by English in their coursework, non-philological students typically have less exposure to the language in their academic studies. The technical jargon in their field, while often presented in English, may not be understood without context or sufficient language skills. Consequently, non-philological students often find themselves struggling with both the academic and specialized vocabulary of their discipline.

3. Anxiety and Self-Confidence – Learning a new language, especially one as complex as English, can lead to anxiety, particularly when students feel they are not making progress quickly enough. Non-philological students may experience increased levels of stress, as their focus is on mastering technical content rather than acquiring a new language. This can hinder both their linguistic and academic development.

4. Limited Opportunities for Practical Use – Non-philological students often do not have as many opportunities to use English in real-world settings. Without the chance to practice speaking or writing in everyday contexts, students may feel disconnected from the practical applications of the language, which can stifle their enthusiasm to learn.

5. Diverse Proficiency Levels – Non-philological students come from varied linguistic backgrounds, which mean their English proficiency levels can differ significantly. This creates a challenge for instructors who need to design lessons that cater to students with differing levels of language skills, from beginners to advanced learners.

To address these challenges, English classes for non-philological students must be designed using pedagogical approaches that promote engagement, relevance, and practical application. Several methodologies have proven effective for this purpose.

1 Task-Based Learning (TBL) – Task-Based Learning (TBL) is a student-centered approach that focuses on the completion of tasks that mirror real-world activities. For non-philological students, TBL offers an effective way to engage with English in a practical context. Tasks can be designed around their specific academic needs and areas of interest. For instance, engineering students could be tasked with reading and summarizing a technical article, while medical students could role-play a doctor-patient interaction in English.

TBL offers several advantages:

It promotes active learning and engagement.

It focuses on meaningful communication rather than just grammar or vocabulary drills.

It helps students see the immediate relevance of the language to their academic and professional lives.

It encourages the use of English in practical contexts, fostering both written and spoken skills.

2 Content-Based Instruction (CBI) – Content-Based Instruction (CBI) integrates language learning with academic content from students' specific fields of study. By teaching English through discipline-related topics, CBI ensures that students acquire both language and subject matter knowledge simultaneously. This approach is highly effective for non-philological students, as it aligns language learning with their academic interests.

For example, a business student might learn English through case studies, while a medical student could study articles related to recent developments in healthcare. This method has several key benefits:

It provides students with authentic materials that are relevant to their academic work.

It bridges the gap between language learning and subject-specific knowledge.

It allows students to expand their vocabulary and comprehension skills in their area of expertise.

3 Blended Learning – Blended learning, which combines traditional classroom instruction with online learning, can be particularly effective for non-philological students. It offers flexibility and personalized learning paths, which are valuable given the varying proficiency levels and schedules of students. Online resources such as video lectures, interactive grammar exercises, and digital forums for group discussions can complement in-class activities.

Blended learning also promotes autonomy, as students can review content at their own pace outside of the classroom. This is especially beneficial for non-philological students, who may need additional time to master specific language skills without disrupting their academic schedules.

4 Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) – Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) emphasizes interaction and communication as the primary goals of language learning. For non-philological students, CLT provides ample opportunities to practice English in realistic contexts, including academic discussions, debates, and presentations. This approach emphasizes fluency over accuracy and encourages students to use English confidently, even when their language proficiency is still developing.

By using authentic materials such as academic lectures, podcasts, and case studies, CLT allows students to experience English as it is used in their academic and professional environments. It also fosters collaborative learning, as students engage in group discussions and projects.

Effective organization of English classes for non-philological students requires attention to various practical factors. These considerations include class structure, materials, assessment methods, and classroom dynamics.

1. Class Structure – Classes for non-philological students should be structured in a way that balances language acquisition with the specific academic needs of the students. A typical class might include:

Warm-up activities to engage students and activate prior knowledge.

Focus on vocabulary related to the discipline, such as technical terms or academic phrases.

Grammar instruction integrated into tasks or contexts rather than isolated drills.

Listening and reading activities that use authentic materials relevant to the students' fields.

Speaking and writing practice focused on discipline-specific scenarios, such as giving a presentation or writing a report.

2. Materials – Materials used in English classes should be authentic and relevant to the students' academic disciplines. Textbooks, academic articles, podcasts, videos, and case studies that reflect real-world situations in the students' fields of study can enhance engagement and relevance. Additionally, technological tools such as language apps, online dictionaries, and forums for peer feedback can be incorporated into the learning process.

3. Assessment – Assessment should focus not only on linguistic accuracy but also on the ability to use English effectively in academic contexts. Assessments can include presentations, written reports, research projects, and participation in group discussions. Formative assessments, such as peer feedback and self-assessment, can also be valuable in tracking progress and promoting learner autonomy.

4. Classroom Dynamics – Instructors should foster a supportive and interactive classroom environment that encourages risk-taking and language use. Non-philological students should be given opportunities to collaborate with their peers, as group work can help build confidence and promote language acquisition. A learner-centered approach, where students are encouraged to take responsibility for their own learning, is particularly effective in this context.

Organizing English classes for non-philological students requires a thoughtful, student-centered approach that prioritizes the relevance and practical application of language learning. By employing methods such as task-based learning, content-based instruction, and communicative language teaching, educators can help students overcome the challenges they face in acquiring English. Furthermore, by integrating authentic materials and aligning learning activities with students' academic needs, instructors can enhance motivation, engagement, and language proficiency. As the demand for English language skills continues to grow across all academic fields, it is essential that educational institutions recognize the unique needs of non-philological students and implement effective strategies for English language teaching that maximize their success.

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